

CONFERENCE THE WELFARE STATE IN PORTUGAL IN THE AGE OF AUSTERITY

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Title Helping in the right way: A new approach to European Welfare State

Abstract

This article aims to clarify a way to reform the Welfare State in Europe and designate a solution to the challenges arising from global inequality and the needs of local inclusion, always through an approach of social/economic justice that not discriminates immigrants or underestimate the problem of unemployment. First dealing with the fact that a Welfare State which is generous with their citizens implies an immigration barrier policy for underdeveloped countries, that would benefit largely the poorest communities in the world, taking into account Branko Milanović's work on global inequality. It was analysed how the Welfare State also failed to secure local inclusion through labor and welfare policies that have promoted high percentages of unemployment in Europe, and how these policies only benefit European middle classes, as said by the Director's law. We propose a reform for the Welfare State that is consistent with free immigration rules and the needs of local inclusion through employment with a focus on the people most disadvantaged. It is also important the feasibility of a limited social welfare to the middle class and focused mainly on wage subsidies for low-income workers, while promotes tax incentives for associations of mutual assistance.

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1. Introduction

Since the first signs of its establishment, the Welfare State has been continuously replicated. In most of Europe, national programs of social security were adopted almost simultaneously. Germany began its social security program in 1889, Sweden in 1909 and the UK in 1911 (Conglenton et al, 2010, p. 2). Other programs were applied later, as the US in 1935 and Switzerland in 1947, supported by right-wing and left-wing during its implementation (Conglenton et al, 2010, p. 2). As said by Conglenton (2010), the programs were well received by liberals [1] and conservatives, which eventually deposit trust in government to provide a safety net for the underserved.

Several large increases in the role of government occurred after the Great Depression and World War II. According to Sping-Andersen (1990) the consolidation of the phenomenon after these events was primarily motivated by political alliances with the new middle class groups, practically a synthesis of the demands of the working class with the demands of the elites. Even with its characteristics varying significantly from nation to nation, the model has remained homogeneous on a global level. It is worth to note that over the time the Welfare State has sometimes been hurriedly fitted into the category of public goods [2], although the concept elasticity does not allow the perfect joint in the non-exclusive and non-rival categories, but could still be perceived as an *impure public good*. Some of the works of James Buchanan (1968) were pioneers in helping to realize these features, such as *The Demand and Supply of Public Goods*.

Roderick Long (1994), following the ideas of Bergstrom (1973, 1986) proposed an approach to the problem of public goods provision and gathered six alternatives: i) Force; ii) Conscience; iii) Delegation; iv) Guarantee v) Privatization; vi) Packaging. These points should be observed, because in the case of the Welfare State generally the solution has been the Force, whose method is to devise, build, run and manage a network of security through the government (Caplan, 2012). Evidence shows that since its appearance the Welfare State experienced an escalation of centralization by the state. As noted by

Congleton (2010), networks of social security had greater decentralization before its full concentration in the state:

*"In the years before the national income security programs were in place, income insurance had been provided by families, private organizations (such as friendly societies, churches, and other private clubs), and by Local Governments."
(Conglenton et al, 2010, p. 2)*

Studies of Buchanan and Tullock (1962) suggest that the practical result of the centralized Welfare State is due to bad incentives provided by government structure, which may also end up increasing the scope of public goods due to some political reasons. Sping-Andersen (1990), one of the greatest theorists of the Welfare State, avoided analyzing the defects of each system and pursue scientific neutrality [3]. By one side the Public Choice authors had asked "what is the State," by another Sping-Andersen questioned "what is the Welfare State". In his analysis identified three main clusters of Welfare State (Liberal, Corporatist and Social Democratic) and observed an incentive called decommodification. An incentive arising primarily from the loss of individual dependence on the labor market, replacing it with other kinds of dependence.

It is important to note that Sping-Andersen's work was concerned about the structural analysis of the phenomenon, avoiding blurring his study with presets on the behavior of power and politics. Simplistic criticism got to be deep enough, such as contend that it is quite inconsistent scoring the phenomenon simply by the amount of government spending, which presume an equal quality for all spending. That still infer a shallow comparison indicated by "more" or "less" Welfare State. In other words, the case is insufficiently understood when limited to the terms of their rights and guarantees. The core of true understanding is to consider how these activities are related to the market and the family's role in social provision (Sping-Andersen, 1990, p. 5).

Considering the web of social relationships, the studies about consequences of *crowding out* effect on Welfare State still need to be keener for a better measurement. In a clear demonstration of the importance of to continue this research line, Feldstein (apud Congleton, 2010, p. 6) argues that a major result of social security is to reduce private savings and cause an advance at the entrance of retirement. A direct result of these incentives. The clustering of social security turns macroeconomic equilibrium most sensitive and dependent of the Welfare State direction, which importance was emphasized by economists as Sanford Ikeda (1997), who sees this latency as part of a *mixed economy*.

Sanford Ikeda, as Sping-Andersen, goes beyond the dichotomy of complete laissez-faire and the pure collectivism to analyze the phenomenon as a social process. One of his proposals is to emphasize the division between Welfare State and regulatory state. The first is focused basically in transfer and redistribute income, unlike the second, which aims to reform the “market failures” and therefore is accompanied by greater instability (Ikeda, 1997, p. 37). Also according to Ikeda, a great vicissitude of this kind of intervention in a *mixed economy* is precisely the distortion in market prices, which lowers allocative efficiency and impairs the functioning of entrepreneurship. This is important to note because the adjustments and pressures suffered by the Welfare State are commonly made by politicians at the expense of economic adjustments.

Even if some broader approaches have been taken, the present work follows the perception of Sping-Andersen (1990) thinking the Welfare State *per se*, rather than giving attention to issues that are more related to the study of individuals behavior and institutions. Combine the practical to the theoretical world is needed if the goal is a real contribution to the reduction of human problems, especially when it is common ideological lettering. The simple and clear assumptions that serve as the motto can be summed up in a few words. Generalized centralization and mild homogeneity of the phenomenon, that will be better explained in the third section with Edmund Phelps’ thesis.

2. Immigration Market

According to Borjas (1994), the first studies that attempted to evaluate the impact of immigration on the economy were made by Barry Chiswick (1978) and Geoffrey Carliner (1980), who analyzed how the immigrants skills adapted in labor market in the country of destination by estimating a cross-section regression model, $\log w_i = X_i\beta + d_i + g_i + \epsilon_i$, where w_i represents the worker and i 's wage rates. Although the analyzes of economic outcomes have evolved, there is still much controversy on the subject. George Borjas, one of the most respected scholars on the subject, along with Lawrence Katz, found that between 1980 and 2000 mexican immigration in the U.S. reduced the total wages of natives by 3.4% in the short term, but in the long run had an impact of 0%. Researchers can even disagree whether the impacts of immigration are positive or negative, but agree that they are really small (Caplan, 2012, p. 6).

Currently about one billion people live on the equivalent of a dollar or less per day (Collier, 2007, apud Caplan, 2012). *The Gallup World Poll* found that more than 40% of adults in the poorest quartile of countries “would like to move permanently” (Clemens, 2011). The product of a widespread poverty is a proportional influx of people around the world looking for better living conditions. Despite all demand for citizenship in most developed nations, the immigration restrictions remain in force for everyone, although economists generally believe that immigration increases the size of the economy, improves productivity and that is beneficial to the most parties (Nowrasteh and Cole, 2013).

The controversial Milton Friedman’s claim “you can not have Welfare State and immigration at the same time” seems to have echoed very negatively, because even his son, David Friedman, today is one of the greatest exponents in defense of *foot-voting*. Maybe the idea of Friedman, the father, was that society would abandon government tutelage on a security system and allow the free immigration, but what happened was exactly the opposite. Immigration barriers remain in effect for the entire world just to prevent “public goods” from being usurped by immigrants in a *free rider* condition. Surely this could have been held in a better context.

It is common to find proposal of humanists reforms to immigration given the fiscal, political, cultural and economic problems, but the main idea is that we should not build walls around the opportunities that benefits a needy people. The walls around the nations, and around immigrants opportunities, would be better positioned around the privileges of the Welfare State (Nowrastesh and Cole, 2013, p. 16), because as will be demonstrated below, stringent immigration barriers can be less utilitarian than a free-flow human environment.

The labor market represents 70% of the entire economy and the work-force is the main product that people sells. Immigration barriers create massive distortions and prohibit literally billions of people to voluntarily sell their work-force for some employers. Clemens (2011), published a very interesting work which analyzed the impacts of immigration barriers in the world GDP. The article *Economics and Emigration: Trillion-Dollar Bills on the Sidewalk?* tried to bring together the state-of-the-art about many topics and came to important conclusions. On the one hand the elimination of trade barriers and capital flows would reach a positive impact of up to 5%, on the other, eliminating the barriers in labor mobility, labor would have estimated gains of 50% - 150% in the global GDP:

Gain Efficiency by Eliminating Barriers for International

(Percent of world GDP)

%	All barriers to labor mobility
147.3	Hamilton and Whalley (1984, Table 4, line 2)
96.5	Moses and Letnes (2004, Table 5, line 4)
67	Iregui (2005, Table 10.3)
122	Klein and Ventura (2007, Table 3)

(Clemens, 2011, p. 3)

The Clemens’ finding is far from triviality, because it is the real proof that the discussion about immigration is undervalued. The flow of human capital can generate economic benefits that would not be possible on any other way. Immigration has suffered several controversies about its accounting, mainly due to the issue complexity, however the

utilitarianism of immigration barriers reduction must take place of a exclusivistic Welfare State.

Back to public goods, should be done some thinking about your loan and use. For example, if a country population doubled on overnight spending on national defense remain the same and the *per capita* public debt would fall by half. On the one hand give money to individuals through the Welfare State is politically attractive, on the other tributes is not. A new design can give simple dispostives which are human with immigrants, such as the voting prohibition and immigrants exclusion in the Welfare State system, but allowing free human flow. Or even allowing the inclusion into the security system after reaching a kind of trigger-amount taxes paid.

If immigrants pay taxes like any other citizen and receive zero benefits, their effects on the tax net would automatically positive (Caplan, 2012, p. 11). If you become permanently out of a social safety net is unfair, there are numerous ways to negotiate such inclusion. Changing the view, if the same criterion is applied to citizens of the same country would eventually be a recipient and other payers of taxes. It would be fair to extradite the recipients? The facts lead to a convergence in the conclusions.

Even with the natives having a natural advantage due to the dominance of the language and therefore higher wages (Nowrastesh and Cole, 2013, p. 3), the dread of immigration remains. If the general picture of the way that immigration is perceived to change, some countries could be observed lançanda the maxim “looking for immigrants” / “vacancies for citizenship”, as already happens with certain skilled jobs and professions. Governments competing for citizens (customers) [4] would be a really good insight, but the real point is a duty of avoid to interfere in voluntary transactions involving immigrants. The demographic arrangement between noncitizens and citizens should be considered.

3. The Challenge of Social Inclusion in Europe

There is a clamour that Europe is a champion in the fight against poverty. In general, it is argued that the amount of their shipments through redistribution (Welfare State) and a protective labor legislation, with strong participation of mandatory collective bargaining (Corporative State) relieves the deprivation of poverty, because it increases income post-transfer (combating absolute poverty) and decreases the distance between those at the base and those at the top (fighting relative poverty).

Clear that the circumstances vary from country to country, and not everyone can claim the same way success in combating poverty of their populations. By the way, this is a key-point, as discussed in the previous section of this article: the consequential social justice focus of European Welfare States is only the own citizens, disregarding the effects on foreigners [5]. According to data analyzed by Branko Milanović (2010) the poorest 5% of Denmark have more income than 90% of world population. However worth to reinforce that lives in Denmark only 5.6 million habitants, which means that 5% represents 280,000 individuals. A low proportion of global population. Thus, the Welfare State would benefit populations on a smaller scale, while the opening of borders would benefit on a global scale.

Occurs which may also question the effort led by European Welfare State in promoting the welfare for their own people. Does this State model effectively provides an inclusion that promises (at least local level – excluding foreigners and/or non-residents)? Amartya Sen (2000) addresses poverty as a deprivation of basic capabilities, not just low income. Although this is a critical factor to consider in developing countries, also is to evaluate the developed countries issues, including the European Welfare States:

“The presence of massive unemployment in Europe (10 to 12 percent in many of the major European countries) entails deprivations that are not well reflected in income distribution statistics. These deprivations are often downplayed on the grounds that the European system of social security (including unemployment insurance) tends to make up for the loss of income to the unemployed. But

unemployment is not merely a deficiency of income that can be made up through transfers by the state (at heavy fiscal cost that can be itself a very serious burden); it is also a source of far-reaching debilitating effects on individual freedom, initiative, and skills. Among its manifold effects, unemployment contributes to the “social exclusion” of some groups, and it leads to losses of self-reliance, self-confidence, and psychological and physical health. Indeed, it is hard to escape a sense of manifest incongruity in contemporary European attempts to move to a more “self-help” social climate without devising adequate policies for reducing the massive and intolerable levels of unemployment that makes such self-help extremely difficult.” (Sen, 1999, p. 21)

Unemployment also affects the attractiveness of immigration itself. According to Johan Noberg (2013), Sweden (his country) is deeply unequal: the gap is not so much between rich and poor, but between those who have a job and those who have not, which is reflected even in an ethnic division – in 2013, 6.4% of Sweden natives were unemployed, while 16% of immigrants were too. Only 2.5% of all jobs in Sweden are low wage, suitable for beginners in the labor market, while the European average is 17%. A characteristic example is the Somali refugees in Sweden. Benny Carlson (apud Noberg, 2006) compared the experiences of Somali immigrants in Sweden with those in Minneapolis, Minnesota. Only 30% of them had a job in Sweden, about half the number who were employed in Minneapolis. Incidentally, in this American city, there are 800 businesses run by Somalis, while there are only 38 in Sweden.

Europe is often remembered as proud for keeping the “income inequality” controlled, not reaching the exacerbated levels of U.S. in terms of the distance between those at the top and those at the base. Is that the increase in income inequality in the U.S., since the 70’s, is considered by many scholars of the area as a result of increased demand for skilled labor in an economy marked by technological advances. Despite Europe also undergoing the same phenomenon, the institutional features of the labor market would have done not so much to react with the increasing of income inequality, but rising unemployment:

“Presumidamente, a mudança tecnológica viesada em favor de trabalhadores qualificados, induzida pela Revolução da Informação, ocorreu simultaneamente

na maioria dessas economias avançadas. Esperava-se, então, que a estrutura salarial desses países tivesse mudado de maneira similar. Muitos pesquisadores observaram que esses países têm instituições no mercado de trabalho bastante diferentes – especialmente no que diz respeito às redes de segurança elaboradas para proteger o bem-estar de trabalhadores com baixas qualificações. Sabe-se também que vários países passaram por tendências diferentes na taxa de desemprego. Nos Estados Unidos, ela declinou em grande parte dos anos 1990 – ao mesmo tempo em que em muitos países da Europa Ocidental ela aumentou rapidamente. Foi sugerido que as mudanças na desigualdade salarial e no desemprego sentidas por esses países são lados inversos da mesma moeda. Os mesmos fatores que levaram ao aumento da desigualdade salarial nos Estados Unidos – onde a estrutura institucional do mercado de trabalho permite que tal dispersão salarial cresça e persista – manifestou-se como maiores taxas de desemprego naqueles países onde mecanismos de salários rígidos não permitem mudanças. Resumindo, o mercado de trabalho respondeu ao aumento na demanda relativa para trabalhadores qualificados ao alterar as quantidades (isto é, os empregos). Em outros países, o mercado respondeu ao alterar os preços (isto é, os salários).” (Borjas, 2010, p. 331)

Borjas (2010) hastens to say that, although the great interest on this hypothesis, it is not yet possible to conclude if the same explanation may lie behind the trends in labor market conditions in the United States compared to other developed countries. Despite this observation, we see that the facts are clear: *if the United States has greater income inequality, Europe has higher unemployment*. The economist Edmund Phelps (2008, p. 2) has developed his work on “economic justice” around the concepts of “dynamism” and “inclusion”: A fair society requires a good economy and a good economy requires high dynamism and an in-depth inclusion.

Economic dynamism is the high degree of innovation into commercially viable directions and there is ample evidence of its presence: a more consistently high level of productivity; meaningful employment in the financing sector; development and marketing of new commercial products, with a frame of managers deciding what and how to produce; higher levels of total labor force and total employment; workers reporting greater “job

satisfaction” and “employee engagement”; a higher rate of “*turnover*” (staff turnover) between the highest rank companies on size or market value, to the extent that a company after another is exceeded (ranking) by companies that did not exist a few decades earlier (Phelps, 2008, p. 2-3).

Counteract the Schumpeterian thesis underlying the notion that high productivity and job satisfaction (with some discussion about job creation) depends of major technological advances made by scientists and explorers, draws attention to the large differences in the dynamics between countries in similar state of the technology use, which is evidenced since the nineteenth century (Phelps, 2008, p. 4). With regard to Europe, it is mentioned that the “*turnover*” among the largest firms is low in France and Italy, and that there is no new member among the 20 largest firms in Sweden since 1921 (Phelps, 2008, p. 4-5).

Moreover, in contrast to the idea that an “industrial policy” directed by the State to encourage innovation, there is too much evidence that corroborates with the design disadvantage, in particular the experience of the twentieth century with these policies, whether in socialist or capitalist countries (Phelps, p. 5). So how is it possible to generate the dynamism without the enlightened scientists or the State control over this process? In theory, it is initiated by Hayek in the 30’s of last century, which the dynamics is generated by an intricate system of introduction and adoption of new methods and products, consisting on creators of commercial ideas, guided by experiences and insights quite different. A variety of entrepreneurs more and more well adapted to their own projects. A diversity of views among the financiers who select entrepreneurs who will be supported throughout the development phase, such as managers/customers with their willingness to embrace new methods and products (Phelps, 2008, p. 6).

Therefore, Dynamism requires Capitalism, despite all the imperfections that this may present. When an economic system with a number of key freedoms is open to business and entrepreneurship, some participants will bring entrepreneurial proposals, others will face uncertainty and fund some of these projects, while corporate managers will evaluate, and sometimes make pioneer adoptions of new methods and products, despite the

uncertainties (Phelps, 2008, p. 6). It is the “animal spirits” that offers entrepreneurs and innovators to invest and create new jobs (Phelps, 2008, p. 6-7).

The appreciation of the dynamism comes from a humanist tradition that dates back to Aristotle and passes the “vitalists” as Cervantes. Based on this tradition, Phelps (2008, p. 9) believes that the dynamism, while causes some floating and some irremediable inequalities, it is necessary for our health, for the good life, since a dynamic economy satisfies some of our most basic needs, like exercising the imagination, experience the mental stimulation provided by the change, having endless series of new problems to solve, expand our capabilities, feel the thrill of discovery and promote personal growth. However, this also leads us to the conclusion that increasingly people need to be included in this dynamic economy and these human goods that it promotes for those who participate. Therefore, economic justice also requires inclusion.

The form favored by Edmund Phelps is the “wage subsidy”. Since the 90’s, has been studying the idea that helping people to help themselves is more effective than give money unconditionally, as this could undermine the motivation to get additional income [6] (Phelps, 2008, p. 9-10). Invoking John Rawls, he believes that people who are healthy in mind and body, but are unable to get jobs suffer a loss of dignity, their self-respect and their sense of participation in society, so we need help people to be included in the job for us to promote the self-respect that Rawls estimated (Phelps, 2008, p. 10).

Occurs that not only self-respect is important. The inclusion in the economy have central importance in people’s lives, because for most people jobs are the most important source of mental stimulation, to solve problems, expansion of talent and self-discovery that they will probably find (Phelps, 2008, p. 10). The dynamism increases the inclusion, even without any government policy to assist this inclusion, however, at the same time is also likely inclusion to have the effect of increasing the dynamism (Phelps, 2008, p. 10).

Understand the importance of the dynamics for a “good economy” directly confronts the notion of “social market economy” advocated in European politics. Phelps (2010, p. 401)

argues that there are two forms of market economy: one that tends to be open to innovative ideas (the “American model”); and one that tends to be more oriented to social services (the “Continental [European] Model”). Contrary to what is usually thought, would be *the first type that raises broader satisfaction and engagement in employment and self-realization*. The first system, called “free enterprise system” or “capitalism”, is characterized by great openness to the implementation of new commercial ideas coming from people in private business, such as great view pluralism among the wealth possessors and financiers about ideas that will be supported by them with capital and necessary incentives for their development; even though much innovation comes from established firms, much also comes from start-ups, particularly the more recent innovations (Phelps, 2010, p. 403).

The second system, called “corporatism”, contains institutions whose purpose is to protect the interests of “stakeholders” and “social partners”, with large employer confederations, big unions and monopolistic banks; model emerged with fascism, but which persisted after the second world war liberalization, incorporating less authoritarian institutions such as co-determination (Phelps, 2010, p. 403). Because of this, Corporatism prevents, discourages, or even blocks changes, such as relocation and entry of new firms. The economy performance will depend on pre-established firms. Everything in cooperation with local and national banks, and lack of flexibility will try to be balanced with the technological sophistication (PHELPS, 2010, p. 403). A widely used strategy is to place companies in a dispute, controlled by the State, to be the “national champion” (Phelps, 2010, p. 406).

Institutions of an economy affect its expected dynamics, because the rate of innovation depends on critical variables, such as the number of people focused on the conception of new ideas (creativity innovative of economy). The economic institutions selectivity in the ideas choice and receptivity to new ideas chosen for development and offered on the market (Phelps, 2010, p. 406). Occurs is that the capitalist system of free enterprise allows better flow of innovative ideas, since the financiers and entrepreneurs do not need to get

approval from the state or social partners, and not need be accountable to these entities if the project goes wrong later, even for financiers investors (Phelps, 2010, p. 406).

So in France, Germany and Italy, labor productivity is lower than in the United States. Continental economies tend to have a labor force participation lower and generally higher unemployment; and the *"World Values Survey"* found that workers from Continental Europe have less job satisfaction and have less pride in their work than their counterparts in the United States (Phelps, 2010, p. 408). For a capitalist economy get greater dynamism than corporatist economies, highlight that the greater desirability of jobs follows, in contrast, also its most precarious (Phelps, 2010, p. 408). This also means that even the most dynamic economy does not create all the time at the same intensity, subjected to cycles in your business activity (Phelps, 2010, p. 410).

To this also joins the fact that unemployment is seen with more anxiety in the United States than in Continental Europe, even if when there is a government compensation on unemployment in both; To Phelps (2010, p. 410), this is explained by the fact that, with greater economic dynamism, there is no a real unemployment compensation because the job becomes a good in itself, so that, as more dynamic, more anxiety at the prospect of unemployment. Therefore, it is paradoxical the americans racket for "job security", as if these jobs were to remain as recruiters and rewarding as before (Phelps, 2010, p. 410). On the other hand, it is true that even relatively dynamic economies suffer from incomplete inclusion of those with less advantage in society, but not greater than corporatist economies since, in the firsts, lower-income workers have access to jobs, while the lasts, they have access to social benefits. The high unemployment rates are overestimated, especially from the perspective of intrinsic stimulating satisfaction on work (Phelps, 2010, p. 410). Thus, it should be noted that the so-called "social market economy", with its strong support for stringent labor laws, negotiations with "social partners" and generous policies of social welfare, is not able to generate enough dynamism and nor sufficient inclusion, unlike their promises.

4. How to overcome the challenges of global justice and local inclusion in the reform of the European Welfare State?

If it is really necessary a *Welfare State* reform, from healthcare to pension system, it is also necessary to take into account how this system has strong relations with labor regulations which potential workers face, such as the regulatory framework in which entrepreneurs face and immigration receptivity, especially to the unskilled. Just checking these interrelationships, it becomes possible to find those who benefit from the status quo of the *Welfare State* in Europe. What social classes most benefit from this scheme?

	Base	2	3	4	Top	Total
Australia 1981	42.8	22.2	13.3	12.5	9.2	100.0
Australia 1985	40.1	24.6	14.4	12.9	8.0	100.0
Belgium 1985	22.9	22.5	21.9	16.6	16.1	100.0
Belgium 1988	21.5	23.6	20.1	16.1	18.7	100.0
Switzerland 1982	38.5	19.2	15.6	13.3	13.3	100.0
Canada 1981	33.0	22.9	17.9	14.1	12.1	100.0
Canada 1987	29.5	24.2	19.2	15.0	12.1	100.0
France 1979	19.7	21.2	18.8	17.7	22.6	100.0
France 1984	17.5	21.8	18.4	17.7	24.7	100.0
Germany 1984	21.8	22.2	16.7	21.0	18.3	100.0
Ireland 1987	32.0	21.9	21.3	15.2	9.6	100.0
Italy 1986	15.6	16.4	19.7	20.7	27.6	100.0
Luxembourg 1985	17.3	18.3	19.5	22.5	22.4	100.0
Netherlands 1983	21.8	21.8	18.4	20.4	17.6	100.0
Norway 1979	34.0	20.9	16.4	13.6	15.1	100.0
Norway 1986	21.5	16.6	14.2	12.2	11.0	100.0
Sweden 1981	18.0	23.9	19.8	19.5	18.7	100.0
Sweden 1987	15.2	25.8	21.7	19.9	17.4	100.0
UK 1979	30.6	20.0	17.4	17.0	15.0	100.0
UK 1986	26.7	25.9	19.4	16.1	11.9	100.0
U.S. 1979	29.7	21.1	17.4	14.7	17.1	100.0
U.S. 1986	29.2	21.2	17.1	17.5	15.1	100.0
Finland 1987	25.9	22.6	18.2	15.8	17.6	100.0

(Mueller, 2003, p. 63)

The table was part of a study involving the nations of the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) and determined the percentage of public funding that goes to each socioeconomic “quintile” of the society through the apparatus

of the existing social welfare. A careful analysis reveals a reality that needs an explanation. In the following countries, France, Italy, Luxembourg and Sweden, tax transfers to the 20% richest (top) outnumber those for the 20% poorest (base). For example, in Italy, for the year 1986, the poorest 20% received 15.6% of transfers, while the richest 20% received 27.6%.

In two countries mentioned above, France and Italy, the transfer tax for the richest 20% exceeds those intended for any other income brackets of society. For example, in France, in 1984, while the richest 20% (the top quintile) received 24.7% of fiscal transfers, all other “quintiles” received less, and the 2nd quintile (the 20% of people who earn less than all other quintiles except base quintile) was the 2nd to have received more transfers, the amount of 21.8%.

In all countries studied, with the exception of Norway in 1986 (but not Norway in 1979), Australia in 1981 (but not in the annex of 1985) and Switzerland, more than 50% of the transfer tax were for “quintiles” intermediaries (the 2nd, 3rd and 4th). For example, even in Australia in 1985, where the transfer intended for the poorest 20% was particularly high (40.1%), the funds allocated to the 2nd, 3rd and 4th quintiles added totaling 51.9%. *That is, in most countries studied over half of fiscal transfer goes to the middle class.*

Only one country has allocated more than 40% of their transfers to the poorest 20%: Australia. On the other hand, Switzerland, Australia and Ireland devoted more than 30% of their transfers to the poorest 20%, and Canada, Norway, United States and United Kingdom did so in one of two years of study for each of these, but not the other year studied. All other countries have spent less than 30% of transfers to the poorest 20%. All countries make transfer to the richest 20% (top). However, only Australia and Ireland allocate less than 10% of transfers to the top, and apart from the previous two, only Canada, Switzerland, Norway in 1986 (but not 1979) and the United Kingdom in 1986 (but not 1979), allocate less than 15% of transfers to the richest 20%.

It is true that the above table reflects the reality of a “clipping” in time. Anyway, it has been argued that the main target of the government's welfare is the middle class, in view of the so called *Director's Law*, proposed by the economist Aaron Director, in which public expenditures are made in primary benefit for middle class and financed by taxes extracted of the poor and the rich class. George Stigler (1970) offered an explanation for their occurrence: a part of society that can ensure control over the state apparatus to employ to improve their own position, and, under certain conditions electoral coalition, this beneficiary will be the middle class. Examples of this would be from minimum wage legislation to the social security and tax reliefs.

Suppose, for approval of certain law, are required 51% of votes are required to win 49%, to approve certain law. If we have a scale (hypothetical) that goes from the poorer (lower extremity) to the richest (higher extremity), nothing requires that 51% are located below, covering the poorest. Rather, it is expected that 51% are positioned in the middle of this scale, as the Law Director.

This is not even a surprise from the point of view of defending the Welfare State, especially the Nordic model. Katrine Kielos (2009, p. 64) defends that one of the three paradoxes behind the success of the Swedish model would be that “help the poor requires benefits for the rich”, since many social programs are universal, such as retirement pensions, health care, child care, education, health insurance, among others, without discriminate the ability to pay; this would mean that by not focusing on low-income people, they can earn more, since the budget for welfare will be higher by also benefit those who can afford, thus evidencing the so-called “paradox of redistribution”.

It is needed to comment on the validity of this paradox. The “paradox of redistribution” was formulated by Korpi and Palme (1998), who concluded that there is a trade-off between selectivity of programs (its focus on the poorest) and the available budget to programs. As much more we focus to benefit the poor, less likely we will reduce poverty and inequality. However, more recent study by Ive Marx, Lina Salanauskaite and Gerlinde Verbist (2013) showed that the correlations that supported the “paradox of

redistribution” in Korpi and Palme’s article have since disappeared, either by changes in the countries that were already in sampling or by addition of new factors in the analysis.

One of the reasons behind the undoing of the “paradox of redistribution” is the changes in “selective” policies of the *targeted systems*. For example, the United States abandoned a major selective federal programs, the AFDC, during the Clinton administration, given their incentives to create an underclass of unmarried mothers chronically dependent of welfare and persisting in poverty and unemployment, replacing it in largely by an expansion of the program also selective (but of a different nature) of the EITC (Earned Income Tax Credit), which is a targeted wage subsidy for low-income workers (Marx; Salanauskaite; Verbist, 2013, p. 31-32).

Therefore, the selective nature of the program affects their effectiveness and efficiency, which *means tested benefits* are no longer exclusively focused on unemployed people, but also to supplement the income of workers in low-paying jobs, as in the RSA (Revenu de Solidarité Active) french or american EITC cited above (Marx; Salanauskaite; Verbist, 2013, p. 32). Considering the points discussed above, a clear answer to the question of who benefits from the current state of the Welfare State: the european middle classes with unionized jobs, composed of people who are either immigrants or are not skilled immigrants. The myth of the Welfare State is that their main target are the poor, and even the poor benefited are opulent if the comparison is made on a global scale.

A successful reform of the Welfare State, therefore, depends on a radical restructuring of the pillars that sustain it. These core principles could be: i) who can bear their own costs, should bear them; ii) who can not afford their costs, can be helped to help himself; iii) consistency with the free immigration; iv) consistency with a market, including labor, more open and flexible. The point about who bears the costs is paramount. James Buchanan (1988, p.20) argues that the “civic religion” of classical liberalism involves a self-confident individual who remains zealous of his own freedom and secure of his own ability to ensure his own well-being in a constitutionally limited state.

Contrary to what some people think, the institutions of a free market incorporate ethics, which prohibits the use of political means (coercion) to gain advantage in the market process and to make a “privatization of the benefit, socializing the costs”. This robust principle can give way to considerations of social justice, not an egalitarian conception of this, but *sufficientarian*. The *sufficientarianism* is a criterion of distributive/social justice according to which the problem is not inequality in the distribution of goods among different people of a society, but some do not have enough of these goods for himself (and his family). That is, what matters is not that people are unequal in wealth and money, but some do not have enough income to meet basic needs.

This concept was mainly developed by Harry Frankfurt (1987, p. 22), according to which the doctrine of egalitarianism (equality as end) distracts people, turning them to esteem the magnitude of the economic benefits available to other people, rather their own needs and interests, in determining their satisfaction with certain level of income or wealth. The moral problem is not the quantitative discrepancy, as measured by lower magnitude of resources possessed by some, but a qualitative discrepancy, measured by the fact that some subjects are in a bad condition, impoverished, so that if there is inequality, but all world is in good condition, there would be no moral restlessness (Frankfurt, 1987, p. 32-33). Misery and poverty are undesirable, but economic inequality by itself is not.

A sufficientarian liberalism is the defense of a society where the only redistributive function of the state is to help the poor, not being allowed any other, and thus would rule out subsidies for middle class and the rich, such as capitalism economic cronyism and corporatism (Teson, 2013). In other words, free market with a social safety net roofing the poorest. But there are several ways to help the poor. From what we discussed earlier about the paradox of redistribution, it seems that one of the most effective ways to do it is through the wage subsidy, where you not only stimulates the income of the poor, as well the employment.

What to Edmund Phelps (2013, p. 120) is consistent with a Rawlsian about economic justice approach, since the theory of justice of John Rawls was not a broad concept that

encompasses the division of anything, such as land or schooling, but on the division of the social surplus arising from the cooperation of people in production, so telling about people who work (or want to do it) and that are part of the economy. Hans-Werner Sinn (2011, p. 424) believes that the Welfare State can be improved by making their redistribution in line with the need of wage flexibility in wage markets, through wage subsidies: the state stops paying for people not participate in the economy, and shall pay them to join.

The Phelps' proposal is different, since it involves offering the subsidy to firms for hiring low-wages workers. In theory both approaches have similar results, since they depend on market adjustments; However, Sinn (2011, p. 425) believes that the proposal to directly pay workers allows better suit to individual circumstances. With that provides the historical end of the old Welfare State based on the payment of the substitute labor income, and the rise of a model based on helping to attend (Sinn, 2011, p. 427).

[1] It is worth noting that the meaning of the word "liberal" has undergone over time several mutations, often used in an opposite direction to the original form. In this article the use of the word is in the North American context, which turned out to insert a new definition of "libertarian".

[2] One of the first to address this problem was Ronald Coase (1910 - 2013). The proposed "Coase Theorem" is to negotiate through the externalities of property rights, provided that the transaction costs are next to zero. Currently there are more obvious signs of the possibility of non-intervention to solve funding problems as the emblematic Kickstarter (crowdfunding), online platform, which has grossed \$ 1 billion and has funded more than 135,000 projects.

[3] Sping-Andersen (1990) in his famous publication *Three Worlds of Welfare Capitalism* had made clear his concern: "A remarkable attribute of the entire literature is its lack of much genuine interest in the Welfare State the such. Welfare State studies have been motivated by theoretical concerns with other phenomena, such as power, industrialization or capitalist contradictions; the Welfare State itself has received scant conceptual Generally attention. If Welfare States differ, how do they differ? And when, indeed, the state is a Welfare State? This turns attention straight back to the original question: what is the Welfare State?"

[4] Borjas made a very astute observation: “it is important to stress the que model only gives only the supply side of the immigration market. Workers who wish to migrate to a particular host country can do so only if the host country's government allows it. The market is highly regulated immigration (Borjas, 1994, p. 1692).” Patri Friedman and Brad Taylor (2011) also did similar observation: “If citizens have a choice of governance providers, they will tend to move to those which best meet their needs. This not only constrains rulers and prevents exploitation, but also enables innovation.”

[5] Michael Huemer (apud Caplan, 2007) made a very peculiar note about the nature of immigration barriers: “Suppose that, through no fault of mine, Marvin is in danger of starvation. He asks me for food. If I refuse to give him food, I thereby fail to confer a benefit on Marvin and, at the same time, allow Marvin to go hungry. If Marvin then starves to death, those who accept the doing/allowing distinction would say that I have not killed Marvin, but merely allowed him to die. And some believe that this is much less wrong than killing, possibly not even wrong at all. But now consider a different case. Suppose that Marvin, again in danger of starvation, plans to walk to the local market to buy some food. In the absence of any outside interference, this plan would succeed—the market is open, and there are people willing to trade food for something that Marvin has. Now suppose that, knowing all this, I actively and forcibly restrain Marvin from reaching the market. As a result, he starves to death. In this situation, I would surely be said to have killed Marvin, or at least done something morally comparable to killing him.”

[6] “In pre-capitalist societies, few workers were properly commodities in the sense that their survival was contingent upon the sale of their labour power [...] De-commodification occurs when a service is rendered as a matter of right, and when a person can maintain a livelihood without reliance on the market. The mere presence of social assistance or insurance may not necessarily bring about significant de-commodification if they do not substantially emancipate individuals from market dependence. Means-tested poor relief will possibly offer a safety net of last resort. But if benefits are low and associated with social stigma, the relief system will compel the most desperate to participate in the market.” (Sping-Andersen, 1990, p. 5)

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